

The Factors Affecting by Leadership and Motivation Working Health Employee at Public Health Centre Kotaraja Jayapura City

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ABSTRACT

Background: Staffs in public health centre are very important resources in public health services to good performance by companies that need labor.

Research Objective: To determine the impact of the Head of Public health centre leadership and motivation on employee performance at the Kotaraja Health Center in Jayapura City.

Methods: Analytical descriptive study using cross-sectional studies. The population is employees at the Kotaraja Health Center with a total sample of 52 people with total sampling. Data obtained using questionnaires and analyzed using chi square and logistic binary regression.

The results of the study: Factors related to the performance of employees at the Kotaraja Health Center are leadership relations between humans (ρ -value = 0.019; RP = 2.424; CI95% = (1.275-4.611)), training technique to be an example (ρ -value = 0.004; RP = 3,016; CI95% = (1,559-5,835)), persuasion and command giving techniques (ρ -value = 0,001; RP = 3,818; CI95% = (1,615 - 9,025)), motivation of the incentive pair (ρ -value = 0,000; RP = 7,273; CI95% = (2,412 - 21,927)) and motivation for participation needs (ρ -value = 0,003; RP = 3,238; CI95% = (1,550 - 6,763)). While the variables used for the performance of Public health centre employees are the boss's techniques of maturing the preparation of followers (ρ -value = 0.510; RP = 1.385; CI95% = (0.663 - 2.891)), the relationship between motivation of employee placement (ρ -value = 0.352; RP = 1.563; CI95% = (0.775 - 3.153)), comfortable working environment (ρ - value = 0,576; .Rp = 1,374; CI95% = (0,676 - 2,792)) and motivation to create healthy competition (ρ -value = 1,000; RP = 1,102; CI95% = (0,528-2,301)). The dominant factor in the performance

of employees at the Kotaraja Health Center is Leadership techniques and persuasion and motivation incentives.

Keyword: Leadership, Motivation, Performance, Staff, Public Health Centre

1. INTRODUCTION

Leadership factors play an important role in improving employee performance, both at the individual, group and at the organizational level. The leader must also try to motivate his subordinates to be able to provide services to the community as an effort to provide assistance and facilities to the people who need access to health (Baki, 2014). Thus to optimize HR in organizations it is necessary to maintain the factors that affect employee performance. Mangkunegara (2009) states that factors that influence performance are leadership factors, motivational factors and ability factors. While Mathis (2007) states that the performance sought by a company from a person depends on the ability, motivation, and support of the individual received. According to Munandar (2008) there is a positive influence between motivation and performance with achievement, meaning employees who have high achievement motivation tend to have high performance, on the contrary those who have low performance are possible because of low motivation. Mulyadi and Rivai (2009) explained that leaders in their leadership need to think about and show leadership styles that will be applied to their employees. The boss's leadership style can

influence the success of employees in achievement (Suranta, 2002).

The Kotaraja Community Health Center is one of the main Puskesmas in the Jayapura City area. Has a large enough service area by supervising 3 urban villages in Abepura District. The Puskesmas is quite respected because it has received several awards such as 3 champions of the Healthy Health Center in Jayapura City, appointed by the Jayapura City Government as a Child Friendly Health Center and several other awards. This is a success to be proud of and must also be maintained in the future (Profile of Puskesmas Kotaraja, 2016). In addition, this Puskesmas is a practice and research field for students from several major universities in the city of Jayapura

Some obstacles occur in Kotaraja Community Health Center organizations such as the lack of participatory staff in implementing Puskesmas activities, rarely attend morning apples every Monday and morning briefings every weekday, reporting that is often late even found there is a person in charge of the program who does not make monthly reports . In the case of making a report, sometimes there is a person in charge who makes the report "as long as possible" without taking into account that these data will be used to assess the performance of the Puskesmas for one year. Lack of collaboration between parts or programs such as there are different data between one program and another program for example under-five visits that differ in the way they are calculated between MCH and Nutrition programs. Although it has often been brokered by the Head of the Puskesmas but often conflicts between employees occur several times just because of trivial problems, besides the disobedience of employees to Puskesmas regulations such as arriving late, leaving the office during service hours without prior notice in the Administration room. Then there is no strict sanction from the Head of the Puskesmas to employees who violate the rules that have been set together so that the employees concerned are sometimes lazy to know the

rules and still violate these rules. Problems occur; the problem must be solved so that the Puskesmas does not become static and dies but must be dynamic according to the times. Based on the above problems, so researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "The influence of the leadership of the Head of the Community Health Center and work motivation on the performance of employees in the Kotaraja Health Center in Jayapura City".

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research is a descriptive analytic study with a cross-sectional study approach, namely data collection is done simultaneously to determine the correlation between the variables studied (Swarjana, 2013). Population is the entire object of research or object under study (Notoatmodjo, 2010). The population in this study were all Civil Servants and Contract Employees at the Kotaraja Health Center in Jayapura City, amounting to 52 people. Samples in this study were not sampled because the population was limited so that the census method was carried out, namely the entire population was used as respondents or also called total sampling. So that the sample used in this study was all civil servants and contract workers at the Kotaraja Health Center, which numbered 52 people.

3. RESULTS

a. Relationship leadership maturation preparation of followers towards employee performance

Table 1. The relationship of leadership maturation of follower preparation towards the performance of employees at the Puskesmas Kotaraja

No	leadership maturation of follower preparation	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Not good	6	46,2	7	53,8	13	100
2	Good	13	33,3	26	66,7	39	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p-value = 0,510; RP = 1,385; CI95%= (0,663 – 2,891)</i>							

Table 1 shows that of the 13 employees who stated that the maturation leadership technique was not as good as 6 followers

(46.2%) on performance and who stated that the maturing leadership technique prepared good followers as many as 7 (53.8%) on performance. While from 39 employees there were 13 people (33.3%) who stated that the followers' preparation maturity leadership technique was not good for performance and as many as 26 people (66.7%) stated with good performance. The chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.510 > 0.05$. This means that there is no relationship between leadership techniques for maturing followers' preparation for the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained $RP = 1,385$; $CI95\% = (0.663 - 2.891)$ does not include 1 which is interpreted that the follower preparation maturity leadership technique is not meaningful to employee performance.

b. Relationship between human relations leadership on employee performance

Table 2. Relationship between human relations leadership on employee performance at Kotaraja Health Center

No	Relationship between human relations leadership	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Not good	8	66,7	4	33,3	12	100
2	Good	11	27,5	29	72,5	40	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p-value = 0,019; RP = 2,424; CI95%= (1,275 – 4,611)</i>							

Table 2 shows that of the 12 employees stated that the leadership technique of human relations is not good as many as 8 people (66.7%) with poor performance and leadership techniques between good human relations as many as 4 people (33.3%) with good performance. Whereas 40 employees stated that the relationship between good human leadership techniques as many as 11 people (27.5%) with poor performance and good relations leadership techniques as many as 29 people (72.5%) with good performance. The chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.019 < 0.05$. This means that there is a relationship between leadership techniques of human relations to the performance of Kotaraja Public Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained $RP = 2,424$; $CI95\% =$

(1,275-4,611) which is interpreted that the bad human relationship leadership technique has the chance of poor performance of 2,424 times higher than the good.

c. Leadership relationships are role models for employee performance

Table 3. Leadership relationships are role models for employee performance on employee performance at Kotaraja Health Center

No	relationships are role models	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Not good	10	71,4	4	28,6	14	100
2	Good	9	23,7	29	76,3	38	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p-value = 0,004; RP = 3,016; CI95%= (1,559 – 5,835)</i>							

Table 3 shows that of the 14 employees stated leadership techniques to be a bad example of 10 people (71.4%) with poor performance and leadership techniques being a good example of 4 people (28.6%) with good performance. While from 38 employees stated leadership techniques to be a good example of 9 people (23.7%) with poor performance and good performance as many as 29 people (76.3%). The chi square test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.004 < 0.05$. This means that there is a relationship between leadership techniques to be an example of the performance of Kotaraja Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained at $RP = 3,016$; $CI95\% = (1,559-5,835)$ which was interpreted to mean that leadership techniques that were not good examples had a chance of poor performance of 3,016 times higher than good.

d. Relationship between persuasion leadership and instructors on employee performance

Table 4. Relationship between persuasion leadership and instructors on employee performance at Kotaraja Health Center

No	persuasion leadership and instructors	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Tidak Baik	14	63,6	8	36,4	22	100
2	Baik	5	16,7	25	83,3	30	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p-value = 0,001; RP = 3,818; CI95%= (1,615 – 9,025)</i>							

Table 4 shows that out of 22 employees stated that persuasion leadership techniques and not good commanders were 14 people (63.6%) with poor performance and 8 good performance (36.4%). Whereas 30 employees stated that persuasion leadership techniques and good commanders were 5 people (16.7%) with poor performance and 25 good performance (83.3%). The chi square test results obtained ρ -value = 0.001 < 0.05. This means that there is a relationship between persuasion leadership techniques and giving orders to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained RP = 3.818; CI95% = (1,615 - 9,025) which is interpreted that persuasive leadership techniques and bad commanders have an opportunity to perform poorly at 3,818 times higher than good.

e. Relationship between motivation to provide incentives to employee performance

Table 5. Relationship between motivation to provide incentives for employee performance at Kotaraja Health Center

No	motivation to provide incentives	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Not good	16	72,7	6	27,3	22	100
2	Good	3	10	27	90	30	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p</i> -value = 0,000; RP = 7,273; CI95%= (2,412 - 21,927)							

Table 5 shows that of the 22 employees, the motivation for giving bad incentives was 16 people (72.7%) with poor performance and good performance of 6 people (27.3%). While from 30 employees, the motivation for giving good incentives was 3 people (10%) with poor performance and good performance as many as 27 people (90%). Chi square test results obtained ρ -value = 0,000 < 0,05. This means that there is a correlation between the motivation of giving incentives to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained Rp. 7,273; CI95% = (2,412 - 21,927) which was interpreted that the motivation for giving bad incentives had an opportunity for

bad performance of 7,273 times higher than good.

f. Relationship between motivation for participation needs on employee performance

Table 6. Relationship between motivation for participation needs for employee performance at Kotaraja Health Center

No	motivation for participation needs	performance of employees				Number	
		Not good		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Not good	12	66,7	6	33,3	18	100
2	Good	7	20,6	27	79,4	34	100
Total		19	36,5	33	63,5	52	100
<i>p</i> -value = 0,003; RP = 3,238; CI95%= (1,550 - 6,763)							

Table 6 shows that of the 18 employees, the motivation for bad participation needs was 12 people (66.7%) with poor performance and good performance of 6 people (33.3%). While from 34 employees stated the motivation for good participation needs as many as 7 people (20.6%) with poor performance and good performance as many as 27 people (79.4%). The chi square test results obtained ρ -value = 0.003 < 0.05. This means that there is a relationship between the motivation of the need for participation in the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained RP = 3,238; CI95% = (1,550 - 6,763) which was interpreted to mean that the motivation for poor participation needs had an opportunity for poor performance of 3,238 times higher than the good.

DISCUSSION

1. Relationship of leadership maturation of followers' preparation towards employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was no relationship between leadership techniques for maturation of followers' preparation for the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. The prevalence ratio test results were obtained RP = 1,385; CI95% = (0.663 - 2.891) does not include 1 which is interpreted that the follower preparation maturity leadership technique is not meaningful to employee performance. This research is in line with what was done by

Wisesa (2016) who conducted research on leadership in effectively motivating employee performance including through the preparation of employee or employee preparation.

Most of the leadership carried out by the Head of the Puskesmas in preparing employees in Kotaraja's Success answered that the head of the Puskesmas explained the Puskesmas vision and mission well, plans to achieve goals, provided guidance, direction and encouragement to subordinates, had communication relations good to subordinates, and provide explanations when you are given a task. According to Pamuji (2010) follower preparation maturation techniques consist of 2 indicators, namely providing clear information and education. Information techniques that are intended to provide clear and factual information to people, so that they can have clear and in-depth information about something that causes the willingness to follow leaders in accordance with their sense, heart and reason.

The statement of employees from cross-distribution results stated that the maturing leadership techniques for preparing followers were not as good as 6 people (46.2%) and good as many as 7 people (53.8%). Whereas 39 employees stated that maturing leadership techniques prepared good followers as many as 13 people (33.3%) and good as many as 26 people (66.7%). This shows that the maturing leadership techniques of follower preparation provide equal opportunities for employee performance. The absence of a relationship between leadership maturation techniques to prepare followers for employee performance is due to the ability of employees in the work to understand the main tasks and functions of each employee, so that employees feel that the actions they do can be done well because the work is the routine of the work they do.

2. Relationship between human relations leadership on employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between leadership

techniques of human relations to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. This research is in line with previous research revealed by Ramadhani (2016), revealing that the role of communication is one of the leadership styles that can influence subordinates in their work. According to Pamuji (2010), revealed that the technique of human relations is a process or series of activities motivating people, namely the whole process of giving motives (encouragement) so that people want to move.

The results of the analysis that the head of the Puskesmas in conducting relations with his subordinates on average answered agreed about the leadership of the head of the Puskesmas in treating employees responsibly, providing comfort in working with his subordinates, taking into account what his subordinates needed, giving freedom to subordinates to cooperate between employee, gives freedom in opinion, respects and respects subordinates, rewards employees who have good performance, involves subordinates in finding solutions to problems that occur and work by showing a friendly attitude. There is a leadership relationship between the Head of the Community Health Center in improving employee performance where employees state that leadership in human relations is not good as many as 8 people (66.7%) lower than the statement of employees who stated good as many as 29 people (72.5%). This shows that the better the leadership relationship with subordinates and other employees increasingly improve employee performance, this is evident from the results of the prevalence ratio test that the relationship between human relations leadership techniques that are not good chance of poor performance is 2,424 times higher than the good.

There is no denying that one of the leadership functions the essential is to communicate effectively. Even opinions that say that a dispute arises, differences in understanding and the existence of conflicts, mainly caused by

the absence of effective communication between parties that are interconnected (Ramadhani, 2016).

There is a relationship or leadership relationship with other employees in improving performance, because in a good relationship will create harmonization and understanding and can influence subordinates to do something in accordance with the expected organizational goals.

3. Leadership relationships are role models for employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between leadership techniques to be an example of the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. Research conducted previously by Suddin (2010) revealed the same thing about leadership styles that are related to employee performance.

According to Pamuji (2010), exemplary techniques are a good example of leaders so that subordinates can follow a good attitude in acting. The leadership technique was exemplified by the Head of the Community Health Center in setting an example, where the Head of the Community Health Center stated that most of the respondents agreed that the head of the Puskesmas gave employees the confidence to get the job done, trusted all decisions made by the leadership, good relations with subordinates, accept criticism, suggestions and opinions from subordinates, act decisively in providing sanctions for employees who violate the rules, give a warning before giving sanctions to employees who violate the rules and make the right decisions.

This respondent's statement shows that generally the respondents agreed and agreed on the actions taken by the Head of the Puskesmas and became role models for other employees. From the results of cross-analysis obtained by the respondents who stated that leadership techniques were not good examples of 10 people (71.4%) with poor performance while employees stated leadership techniques to be a good example with good performance as many as 29

people (76.3%). This shows that if leadership can be a good role model, it can improve better performance. Conversely, if the example done is not good can have an impact on the performance of employees who are not good. This is evidenced also from the results of the prevalence ratio test that leadership techniques to be a bad example have the opportunity to have a bad performance of 3,016 times higher than the good ones. The findings in this study indicate that good and bad performance is strongly influenced by the exact style leadership applied by the Head of the Puskesmas as leaders should pay more attention to subordinates and provide good examples of work, so that they can be role models for employees such as timely work attendance, fair incentives and not choosing - choosing employees to provide sanctions or rewards.

4. Relationship between persuasion leadership and order giver on employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was a relationship between persuasion leadership techniques and giving instructions to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees. These results are consistent with the research conducted previously by Wijayanti (2012), that there is a leadership relationship in an effort to influence many people through communication to achieve goals, how to influence people with instructions or orders, actions that cause other people to act or respond and cause positive changes. Important dynamic forces that motivate and coordinate organizations in order to achieve goals, the ability to create confidence and support among subordinates so that organizational goals can be achieved.

According to Pamuji (2010), the persuasion technique and the order giver show an atmosphere where between the position of the leader and subordinates there are no clear boundaries, so the leader cannot use his power and power, while the technique of giving orders is to instruct people to obey that gives orders to do

something. Actions of leadership in providing acts of persuasion to subordinates to the performance of employees by helping subordinates or employees in achieving goals, placing employees according to their respective expertise, delegating tasks according to the abilities and expertise possessed by subordinates and paying attention to conflicts that occur in employees and responding.

Persuasive communication technique is one technique motivating employees to work by influencing employees extrologically. Fulfilment of factors from the work will lead to job satisfaction that affects work motivation, while factors from outside the work will eliminate job dissatisfaction which results in increased morale and performance (Slamet, 2007: 204).

The prevalence ratio test results stated that persuasive leadership techniques and bad commanders have an opportunity to perform poorly at 3.818 times higher than good. This is considered by employees as one of the important factors that encourage to increase productivity and their performance due to indirectly influential communication that provides motivation which has an impact on the performance of employees who are increasing. This is also recognized by employees where persuasion leadership techniques and giving orders are not good (63.6%) performance is not good otherwise the employee states persuasion leadership techniques and good commanders as much as 83.3% with good performance.

5. The relationship of motivation to provide incentives to employee performance

The results of the study showed that the motivation for providing incentives was related to the performance of employees at the Kotaraja Health Center. This research is in line with previous research conducted by Bawono (2015) which states that giving incentives has a positive relationship and a significant effect on employee performance. Respondents about giving 72.7% of bad incentives while motivation in giving good

incentives as much as 90% had good performance, where the incentive motivation that did not have the chance of bad performance was 7.273 times higher than employees who got good incentives. .

In giving motivation to provide incentives expressed by Kotaraja Health Center employees by the leadership, most of whom agreed because leaders gave awards to employees who had good performance, the appreciation or praise of subordinate positive ideas, gave praise to subordinates for the work achievement achieved by subordinates, giving awards for employee work performance and giving gifts to subordinates so that subordinates are always eager to work. Incentives are awards in the form of money given by the organization leaders to employees so that they work with high motivation and achievement in achieving organizational goals (Mangkunegara, 2012). Providing appropriate incentives can be a stimulus or a tool to motivate employees to work and always provide good performance. Basically the wages of nurses who are in the same position are the same, but the rewards received by nurses every month can be different. The cause is an incentive that causes differences that are received by the employee.

Incentives are in the form of money or services that are added to employee salaries which are usually reserved for employees who have done a good job. If payment basic salary to employees is usually carried out every month, then incentive payments are carried out varying depending on criteria such as annual turnover and the number of patients obtained. Kotaraja Health Center also provides incentives to employees to support their work performance (Risnawati, 2018).

6. The relationship of motivation fulfills the need for participation in employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was a correlation between the motivation of the need for participation in the performance of Kotaraja Community

Health Center employees. This research is in line with previous research conducted by Rahayau (2017) which revealed that in participatory needs, where employees can actualize themselves and this causes a sense of appreciation for themselves and raises employee morale that implies the performance they do. The employee's response to the needs of participation carried out by the leadership mostly agreed that the Leader gave criticism and suggestions for improving employee performance, giving direction so that the employees were focused on achieving the goals of the Puskesmas, coordinating the achievement of the Puskesmas goals, while the employee's statement was disagreeable, do not often supervise for optimal work results and sincerity of leadership in communicating with subordinates.

Human resources are one of the existing resources in a company besides other resources such as capital, materials and machinery. The company also needs human resources, namely employees. Employees are an important resource for the company, because they have the talent, energy and creativity that are needed by the company to achieve its goals. Someone who works will feel more valued by the surrounding community, than those who don't work (Hasibuan, 2012: 44).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded as follows

1. There is no relationship between leadership techniques for maturation of followers' preparation for the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees (ρ -value = 0.510; RP = 1.385; CI95% = (0.663 - 2,891))
2. There is a relationship between the leadership techniques of human relations to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees (ρ -value = 0.019; RP = 2,424; CI95% = (1,275-4,611)).
3. There is a relationship between leadership techniques to be an example of the performance of Kotaraja Community Health

Center employees (ρ -value = 0.004; RP = 3.016; CI95% = (1,559-5,835)).

4. There is a relationship between persuasion leadership techniques and the instructor on the performance of Kotaraja Public Health Center employees (ρ -value = 0.001; RP = 3.818; CI95% = (1,615 - 9,025)).

5. There is a relationship between motivation to provide incentives to the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees (ρ -value = 0,000; RP = 7,273; CI95% = (2,412 - 21,927)).

6. There is a relationship between motivation for participation needs on the performance of Kotaraja Community Health Center employees (ρ -value = 0.003; RP = 3.238; CI95% = (1,550 - 6,763)).

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